

Comparison of average diametric growth and radial growth of *R. solani* in *A. marmelos* essential oil.

peated four times with three replications each time.

Treated petri plates were incubated at $28 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The data were computed by the formula $3.14 \times r^2$ (area measurement technique). The average diametric growth was always less than total radial growth (see figure).

Differences of a given growth ranged between 0.99 and 25%. When inhibition was 50% with the diametric growth measurement method, the same growth was only 25% by the area measurement method.

The difference increased from 0 to 50%, then decreased from 51 to 100%—the difference at 51% corresponds to the difference at 49, etc. There is a consistent 0.02% decrease between two adjacent units calculated by the area measurement method.

The method holds good for both sporulating and nonsporulating fungi. When fungal growth was irregular, however, this method was not accurate either. □

Joint infection of rice by *Sclerotium oryzae* Catt., *Sclerotium rolfsii* Sacc., and *Monographella albescens*

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During disease surveys of several foothill and upland ricefields in four districts of Manipur 1985-86, we noticed cases of sheath rot (ShR) fungus *Monographella albescens* (Thumen) Parkinson, Sivanesan and Booth associated with stem or foot rot disease. We collected 100 ShR-

diseased rice plants randomly from Imphal, Thoubal, Bishnupur, and Senapati districts. Those that also showed symptoms of stem- and foot rot-disease were separated and the disease isolated on potato dextrose agar (PDA).

Potted rice plants were inoculated at the late boot stage with 5-d-old cultures of *S. oryzae* or *S. rolfsii*; control plants were treated with PDA medium alone. When disease symptoms appeared, prepared mycelial fragments from a 6-d-old culture of ShR fungus were sprayed on both diseased and control plants. Inoculated plants were maintained at 90% relative humidity.

Only two sclerotium-producing fungi, *S. oryzae* and *S. rolfsii*, were consistently associated with ShR (Table 1). The association of *M. albescens* with *S. oryzae* was higher than with *S. rolfsii*.

Rice plants infected with either *S. oryzae* or *S. rolfsii* were significantly more susceptible to ShR fungus (Table 2). □

Table 1. Association of *M. albescens* with *S. oryzae* or *S. rolfsii*. Manipur Agricultural College, Imphal, India, 1985-86.

District	Plants analyzed (no.)	<i>M. albescens</i> association (%) with	
		<i>S. oryzae</i>	<i>S. rolfsii</i>
Imphal	100	8	2
Thoubal	100	5	4
Bishnupur	100	10	3
Senapati	100	6	3

Table 2. Severity of *M. albescens* on rice plants infected with either *S. oryzae* or *S. rolfsii*. Manipur Agricultural College, Imphal, India, 1985-86.

Source of infection	<i>M. albescens</i>		Disease incidence (%)
	Plants inoculated (no.)	Plants infected (no.)	
<i>S. oryzae</i>	20	19	95
<i>S. rolfsii</i>	20	17	85
Control	20	5	25
LSD (0.05)	-	3	-

Influence of carbendazim concentration on in vitro production of pectinolytic and cellulolytic enzymes by *Rhizoctonia solani*

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We studied the effect of different concentrations of carbendazim on in vitro production of pectinolytic and cellulolytic enzymes by *R. solani*.

The culture filtrates of *R. solani*

obtained by growing the fungus in Czapek's pectin broth were treated with different concentrations of the fungicide (0, 0.01, 0.05, and 0.1%) and assayed for production of protopectinase, polygalacturonase, polygalacturonate *trans* eliminase, and pectin *trans* eliminase. The activity of the enzymes cellulase (C₁), cellulase

(C_x), and β-glucosidase also were estimated.

Production of protopectinase, polygalacturonase, polygalacturonate *trans* eliminase, and pectin *trans* eliminase by *R. solani* was markedly inhibited in all concentrations of carbendazim (see table). Highest reduction was in 0.1% concentration.

Activity of cellulase (C₁) and cellulase (C_x) also was markedly inhibited. Highest inhibition of cellulase (C₁) and cellulase (C_x) activities was in 0.1% concentration.

Increases in carbendazim concentrations increased β-glucosidase activity. The increase was highest in 0.1% concentration. □

Influence of carbendazim concentrations on in vitro production of pectinolytic and cellulolytic enzymes by *R. solani*.

Fungicide concentration (%)	Proto pectinase production ^a	Poly galacturonase production ^b	Poly galacturonate <i>trans</i> eliminase production ^c	Pectin <i>trans</i> eliminase production ^d	Cellulase activity units (C ₁)	Cellulase activity units (C _x) ^e	β-glucosidase ^f activity
0 (control)	++++	48.50	34.4	22.3	3.500	41.10	3.000
0.01	+++	32.60	24.7	17.1	2.350	30.33	3.532
0.05	++	28.50	18.8	13.4	1.797	25.54	4.246
0.1	+	8.10	8.5	6.4	0.812	13.22	4.925

^a Maceration of potato disc, + to ++++ = increase in activity. ^b Percent loss in viscosity of 0.75% sodium polypectate after 120 min. ^c Percent loss in viscosity of 1.2% sodium polypectate after 120 min. ^d Percent loss in viscosity of 1% citrus pectin after 120 min. ^e Percent loss in viscosity of 0.5% carboxy methyl cellulose after 120 min. ^f mg of reducing sugars liberated from 1% arbutin/100 ml.

Evaluating fungicides to control rice leaf scald (LSc) in the field

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We tested five fungicides against LSc *Gerlachia oryzae* Has. and Yokogi under field conditions 1987-88.

Rice cultivar Lalat was planted in 4 × 5-m plot at 15 × 20-cm spacing in a randomized block design with three replications. Plants were artificially inoculated during the evening 25 d after transplanting (DT) with a suspen-

sion of 30,000 spores/ml, using a plastic atomizer.

Seed treatment involved soaking seeds in carbendazim + thiram suspension for 12 h before sowing. Fungicides were sprayed at 30, 40, and 50 DT. Disease incidence was measured 55 DT.

Seed treatment with carbendazim + thiram was effective. Among spray treatments, thiophanate-methyl was most effective in reducing disease (see table). Carbendazim and maneb also significantly reduced disease. No phytotoxicity occurred in any treatment. □

Tungro (RTV) incidence in wetbed seedling nursery

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Rice farmers often raise nurseries in areas adjacent to the fields. Unprotected nurseries are suspected to play an important role in the spread of RTV.

We studied RTV incidence on rice seedlings in an unprotected wetbed nursery. Pregerminated TN1 seeds were sown in a 2 × 10-m nursery laid out in the middle of a field planted to TN1 with high RTV incidence.

At 21 d after seeding (DM), green leafhopper (GLH) in the nursery and in the plants surrounding the nursery were sampled by 10 sweeps of an insect net. GLH infectivity was tested by introducing one captured vector into a test tube containing a TN1 seedling for 24-h inoculation. Seedlings were indexed for RTV by ELISA 3 wk later.

At 21 DAS, seedlings in the field nursery were pulled and apportioned to cover four 7.5 × 8-m plots in the insect-proof screenhouse and four 5.5 × 9-m plots in the field. Two to three

Control of rice LSc disease by fungicides. Bhubaneswar, India, 1987-88.

Treatment	Application rate (kg/ha)	Disease incidence ^a (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
		1987	1988	1987	1988
Carbendazim + thiram (1:1) ^b	0.035 + 0.105	25.00 (28.31)	28.80 (32.45)	2.5	2.4
Carbendazim	0.8	16.80 (24.19)	27.20 (31.43)	2.8	2.5
Thiophanate-methyl	0.8	11.07 (19.43)	19.60 (26.27)	2.9	2.9
Maneb	1.0	23.20 (28.79)	27.90 (31.88)	2.7	2.4
Blitox	1.0	27.40 (31.56)	29.90 (33.14)	2.6	2.3
Control (unsprayed)		41.93 (40.35)	46.10 (42.76)	2.2	1.8
LSD (0.05)		2.4	2.28	0.3	0.3
(0.01)		3.41	3.24	0.4	0.3

^a Figures in parentheses are the transformed angular values. ^b Chemicals used as seed treatment.